

Integrating Agile Methodologies in Software Design Education: A Capstone Approachⁱ

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The increasing adoption of agile methodologies in the software industry necessitates their integration into software engineering education. Traditional instructional approaches often fail to provide students with the iterative and collaborative experiences required in real-world development environments. This brief paper presents the CMPSC 483w Software Design Methods, a capstone course at Penn State University Brandywine, which leverages agile principles, specifically Scrum, to enhance both technical proficiency and professional competencies in students. The course is structured around project-based learning and emphasizes industry alignment, ensuring that graduates possess the skills necessary to succeed in modern software engineering roles.

Modern software development relies heavily on agile methodologies, particularly Scrum and Extreme Programming (XP), to manage project complexities and accommodate evolving requirements. However, many traditional software engineering courses focus primarily on theoretical concepts, leaving graduates underprepared for industry expectations. CMPSC 483w at Brandywine, addresses this gap by embedding agile practices into its curriculum, fostering experiential learning through team-based, real-world projects.

Empirical research underscores the efficacy of agile frameworks in education [1]. Studies indicate that project-based learning, coupled with iterative methodologies, enhances student engagement and comprehension [2]. Collaborative learning fosters essential professional skills, including teamwork and adaptability [3]. Additionally, Sommerville highlights that students trained in agile methodologies demonstrate superior problem-solving abilities and resilience in handling project uncertainties [4].

Despite its advantages, agile education presents challenges such as a steep learning curve and resistance to non-traditional instruction methods [5]. However, structured mentorship, industry partnerships, and continuous curriculum refinement can mitigate these challenges and improve educational outcomes.

CMPSC 483w employs an experiential, project-based pedagogical model and its learning methodology is an amalgam of constructivism, situated learning, Kolb's experiential learning cycle, and cognitive apprenticeship, that mirrors professional software development environments, aiming to enhance learning outcomes. Key components include:

- **Agile-Based Learning:** Students work in teams, participating in sprint planning, development cycles, and retrospective evaluations [6].
- **Project-Centric Approach:** The course follows a capstone model where students as agile self-organizing teams with the help of product owners shape their own project idea and then design, implement, test, and deploy a functional software product.
- **Industry Alignment:** The curriculum integrates real-world case studies and industry feedback to ensure relevance.

- Continuous Feedback and Iteration: Regular stakeholder meetings, peer assessments, and iterative refinement enhance learning outcomes.
- Interdisciplinary Skill Development: Students develop both technical and professional skills, including communication, project management, and critical thinking [6].

The agile development cycle adopted in the course [7] includes planning, literature review, prototyping, development, testing, deployment, and final project presentations.

Graduates of CMPSC 483w acquire competencies in:

- Problem-solving, teamwork, and adaptability.
- Written and verbal communication.
- Technical proficiency, including coding and system design.
- Analytical thinking and attention to detail.

Students are assessed through project deliverables (50%), presentations and video demonstrations (20%), peer assessments (20%), and team participation (10%).

CMPSC 483w serves as a model for integrating agile methodologies into software engineering education with a particular focus on skills development [8]. Future iterations may incorporate AI-assisted development tools and expand industry collaborations and more active involvement. By continually refining the curriculum, institutions can better prepare students for dynamic and evolving software engineering careers. Initial evaluations show that students highly evaluate the course mentioning that they are extremely motivated, and they enjoy the learning experience.

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